

Soil amendments in plant disease control

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The use of nonedible oil cakes and other agricultural and industrial by-products as important tools in biological control of plant pathogens has been recently recognized. Soil amendments encourage growth and multiplication of soil microflora and thus kill pathogens in soil by competition or antibiosis.

A field experiment at RRS in Moncompu during the 1978–79 punja (Oct–Jan) season studied the effect of various nonedible oil cakes and other by-products on the intensity of sheath

blight and sheath rot disease of rice.

The intensity of both diseases was lower in amended plots than in unamended plots. The results indicate that the oil cakes and other organic materials tested were equally efficient in suppressing sheath blight and sheath rot (see table). The benefit may be due to stimulation of soil saprophytes leading to a reduction in the pathogen population or to better plant tolerance because of increased nutrition offered by the amendment.

Oil cakes are also useful as insect and rodent repellent and as nitrogen inhibitor. Amending the soil with nonedible cakes will be a good practice in rice cultivation. ■

not only the fungal pathogen, but also by a *Trichoderma* sp. When sterilized rice straw was mixed with the *Trichoderma* and the sheath blight pathogen, the straw decomposed fast when mixed with *Trichoderma* alone. Speed of decomposition was lower with *Trichoderma* plus sheath blight pathogen, and slowest with the sheath blight pathogen alone. In a mixture, a large number of dead sclerotial bodies of *T. cucumeris* were recovered, and the mycelium was found coiled with the *Trichoderma* mycelium. ■

Effects of treatment with various by-products on the intensity of sheath blight and sheath rot. Kerala, India.

Treatments	Disease score ^a (0-9)	
	Sheath blight	Sheath rot
Neem cake (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>), 1 t/ha	2.33	1.93
Marotti cake (<i>Hydrocarpus</i> sp.), 1 t/ha	2.33	2.33
Rubber seed cake (<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>), 1 t/ha	2.73	2.46
Puma cake (<i>Callophyllum inophyllum</i>), 1 t/ha	2.86	2.06
Coconut pith (<i>Cocos nucifera</i>), 2 t/ha	2.46	2.60
Sawdust, 2 t/ha	3.40	3.00
Rice husk (<i>Oryza sativa</i>), 2 t/ha	2.86	2.73
Untreated control	7.26	7.00
C.D. (0.05)	1.67	1.72

^aStandard Evaluation System for Rice scales. Sheath blight: 1 = lesions limited to lower 1/4 of leaf sheaths. 9 = lesions reaching top of tillers; severe infection on all leaves. Sheath rot: 1 = less than 1% [of tillers affected] (= to resistant check). 9 = 50-100% (= no susceptible check).

Ecology of the rice sheath blight pathogen: saprophytic survival

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It has been well established that the sclerotial bodies of the rice sheath blight pathogen *Thanatephorus cucumeris* serve as the primary inoculum source for initial infection. In temperate regions these sclerotia, usually numbering 1,000/m², overwinter in the soil after the rice harvest. An initial attempt at IRRI, a tropical region, indicated that in a field of more than 50% infection, only a small number of sclerotia could be recovered. Previous results indicated that many of the sclerotia in the

field were colonized by bacteria, many of which were antagonistic to the fungus.

The saprophytic survival of the pathogen was therefore studied by burying healthy rice straw pieces (2–3 cm apart from the internode) in unsterilized soil of dryland origin. The soil was mixed with different amounts of inoculum and incubated for 1 month under conditions of submergence, and 100% and 50% moisture saturation. The percentage of rice straw colonization by the fungus was lower under submergence than in 50% saturation. When infected rice straw pieces were buried in soil of dryland origin, recovery of the fungus was lower in unsterilized than in sterilized soil. In unsterilized soil and at 50% moisture saturation, a high percentage of the straw was colonized by

Reaction of wetland rice to dirty panicle disease and the influence of soil type and fertilization

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Dirty panicle disease of rice is becoming a major disease in Nigeria with the introduction of improved varieties and high-input technology. The disease has been observed on rainfed dryland rice, but incidence is higher on rainfed wetland rice. Although the precise extent of damage is not known, national rice pathologists associate the disease with a loss in quality of parboiled-milled rice because of the black grains.

In the 1979 wet season (Jun–Oct), the disease was widespread in trials at the Badeggi Rice Research Station and in neighboring rainfed wetland rice farmers' fields. A cooperative investigation was initiated on an acid Oxisol (Agaie soil series) to evaluate the performance of 5 recommended rice cultivars with 12 fertilizer treatments (see table) when exposed to dirty panicle disease under rainfed wetland conditions. Twenty-one-day-old seedlings of each cultivar were transplanted in a 30- × 36-m plot divided into 12 equal parts, 6 × 3 m each. The cultivars were scored for dirty panicle disease incidence during the grain-maturing stage.

IR8 and FARO15 (IR8/BG79) were least infected, suggesting varietal resistance. IR20 and SML140-10 were moderately susceptible, and MAS2401

Reaction of wetland rice cultivars to dirty panicle disease and the influence of fertilization on the disease. Badeggi, Nigeria, 1979 wet season.

Fertilizer	Reaction to dirty panicle disease ^a					
	SML140-10	MAS2401	FARO15	IR8	IR20	Mean
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	2.5	5.5	1.5	1.5	3.5	2.9
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₀	2.5	3.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.3
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀	2.5	8.5	1.5	3.5	2.5	3.7
N ₁₂₀ P ₃₀ + 30K ₆₀	2.5	8.5	5.5	1.5	1.5	3.9
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₃₀ + 30	3.5	5.5	2.5	1.5	3.5	3.3
N ₁₂₀ P ₃₀ + 30K ₃₀ + 30	5.5	4.5	2.5	1.5	4.5	3.7
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + Zn ^b	2.5	4.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.5
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + lime ^c	2.5	3.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.3
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + ash ^d	2.5	3.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.3
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + Mg ^e	1.5	2.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	1.9
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + Si ^f	1.5	2.5	1.5	1.5	2.5	1.9
N ₁₂₀ P ₆₀ K ₆₀ + Zn + Mg + Si	2.5	2.5	2.5	1.5	2.5	2.3
Mean	2.8	4.6	2.1	1.7	2.8	

^a 1-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately susceptible, 7-9 = susceptible. ^b 2% ZnO as zinc sulfate. ^c 5 t slaked lime/ha. ^d 5 t straw ash/ha. ^e 40 kg MgO/ha as magnesium sulfate. ^f 80 kg SiO₂/ha as sodium metasilicate.

was susceptible. Unbalanced fertilization (application of NPK only) increased disease incidence in resistant, moderately susceptible, and susceptible cultivars; however, liming or application of straw ash or Mg or Si (in addition to NPK) reduced the disease incidence significantly

in all cultivars (see table).

Isolations from infected panicles suggest that the primary causal organisms of dirty panicle disease are *Curvularia* spp., particularly *C. lunata*, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and *Nigrospora* spp. (most prevalent in susceptible cultivars). ■

Ecology of the rice sheath blight pathogen: parasitic survival

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The host range of *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, the rice sheath blight pathogen, is wide and includes many weed species. In an initial field experiment with direct-seeded and unweeded IR36, both rice and weeds

became infected when the inoculum of the fungus was broadcast on the field. Many weed species including *Echinochloa colona*, *E. glabrescens*, *E. crus-galli* ssp. *hispidula*, and *Monochoria vaginalis* were as susceptible as rice. A subsequent survey of the IRRI farm showed many weeds of the Gramineae family in the rice fields naturally infected with the rice sheath blight pathogen (see table). The symptoms were identical to those on rice. In fallow or idle fields under wetland conditions, sclerotial bodies and

Some weed hosts of sheath blight organism at IRRI, 1979.

Species name	Family	Plant part isolated	Where collected
<i>Chloris</i> sp.	Gramineae	Sheath	Dryland
<i>Cleome rutidosperma</i>	Capparidaceae	Leaf, pod, seed	Wetland
<i>Digitaria</i> sp.	Gramineae	Blade	Wetland
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	Gramineae	Blade sheath	Wetland Dryland
<i>E. crus-galli</i> ssp. <i>hispidula</i>	Gramineae	Sheath	Wetland
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	Gramineae	Sheath	Wetland
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	Pontederiaceae	Leaf	Wetland
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i>	Gramineae	Sheath	Wetland
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	Gramineae	Blade, sheath	Wetland
<i>Rottboellia exaltata</i>	Gramineae	Blade	Dryland
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Gramineae	Blade	Dryland

sometimes the basial stage of the fungus could be observed on those weeds. A pathogenicity test of isolates obtained from the weeds suggested that they were highly virulent to rice. These weeds obviously are not only hosts for the fungus but also and, perhaps more important, the source of inoculum to infect the rice crop. ■

A theoretical model for ufra control

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Cox and Rahman have suggested that ufra disease of deepwater rice in Bangladesh, caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev, might be controlled by any procedure that prolongs the overwinter decay phase of the nematode population in infested crop residues left in the field from the previous season. Such methods include the sowing of early maturing varieties (even though they might have to be harvested from a boat), late sowing (risking early flood damage), or transplanting after the floods arrive (if floodwaters do not rise too quickly). A cost is clearly associated with each procedure. The optimum extension of the decay phase will be determined by a trade-off between the yield gain through pest control and the yield loss associated with adoption of the procedure, even in the absence of any disease (see figure).

The function $Y' = f(t)$ shows the potential yield that might be expected in the absence of disease as a result of postponing the time of sowing or transplanting. The yield falls off as the ground becomes too wet for sowing (even using pregerminated seed), or as the water becomes too deep for transplanting or, in shallow situations, as flowering time approaches. The function $Y'' = f(t)$ shows how the potential yield increases, in the absence of physiological losses, as the time of sowing or transplanting is postponed as a result of ufra control through prolongation of the overwinter decay phase. If the crop technology is